

Polycyclic Systems. Part XVIII.¹ Synthesis of Methyl 2-(1-Naphthyl)-5-Oxocyclopent-1-enylacetate, Methyl β -5-(1-Naphthyl)-2-Furylpropionate, and a Few Related Compounds

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The furfurylidene derivative of 1-acetylnaphthalene on acidic hydrolysis affords a mixture of acids which on successive treatment with alkali and methanolic hydrogen chloride yields methyl 2-(1-naphthyl)-5-oxocyclopent-1-enylacetate(III) and methyl β -5-(1-naphthyl)-2-furylpropionate(V) in 50 : 50 ratio. The formation of the furanoid compound is atypical but not unusual. The dynamic n.m.r. of the ketoester(III) indicates a low energy barrier to rotation about the aryl-cyclopentenone bond. 2-*p*-Methoxyphenyl-5-oxocyclopent-1-enylacetic acid(X) is likewise prepared and found to resemble closely a byproduct reported to arise from an alleged acid-induced dicyclisation of 4, 7-diketo-7-*p*-methoxyphenylheptanoic acid(VIII) and to which a phenalenone structure(IX) was given.

DURING our studies on restricted rotation in some arylcyclohexenone derivatives,^{2,3} the highest barrier (22.8 kcal mol⁻¹) was encountered in methyl 2-(1-naphthyl)-6-oxocyclohex-1-enylacetate(I) originating from a peri-interaction between 8-H of the naphthyl and 3-H of the cyclohexenyl ring. In that context, we thought that a similar study on a related cyclopentenone system (*e.g.*, III) would reveal some basic difference in the geometry of cyclohexenone and cyclopentenone moiety. *A priori*, the latter with a more or less flat ring would offer less steric resistance to any neighbouring atom or group across the pivotal bond. It is indeed found that while the coalescence temperature of the AB-quartet of the side-chain methylene protons in (I) is 183°, the same for (III) is below -90°. The synthesis of methyl 2-(1-naphthyl)-5-oxocyclopent-1-enylacetate(III) is modelled after the well-known procedure of Robinson⁴ for the 2-naphthyl analogue but is not exactly typical⁵⁻⁷. This and the synthesis of a few related compounds which may hopefully resolve the structure of an allegedly unusual byproduct during acid-induced athanolysis of furfurylidene *p*-methoxyacetophenone⁸ form the subject matter of this communication.

1-Acetylnaphthalene was condensed with furfuraldehyde in presence of aqueous alkali to give the furfurylidene derivative which resisted all attempts to crystallise. The n.m.r. spectrum, τ (CCl₄, 100 MHz) 1.65 (1 H, d, *J* 9 Hz, 8-H), 2.10-2.40 (4 H, m, 4ArH), 2.45-3.00 (5 H, m, 3ArH+2 vinylic H), 3.49 (1H, d, *J* 3.3 Hz, 3'-H), and 3.65 (1H, m, 4'-H),

however, agreed well with the structure(VI). It was hydrolysed by boiling hydrochloric acid first in ethanol and then in acetic acid,^{4,7} to furnish an acidic product (yield, 50%) which proved to be a 50 : 50 mixture of 4,7-diketo-7-(1-naphthyl)heptanoic acid(VII) and β -5-(1-naphthyl)-2-furylpropionic acid(IV), the integration of the two furyl protons (4-H and 3-H) at τ 3.45 and 3.82 giving an accurate measure of the ratio. This appears to be the first example of a furan-derivative being formed under this condition although alcoholysis of analogous furfurylidene ketones in dry butanol⁹ or ethanol¹⁰ saturated with hydrogen chloride is known to give furanoid compounds. In the present case, ring-closure takes place in presence of water and seems to be facile due to the partial release of steric strain inherent in 1-naphthoyl system. Rate enhancement of cyclisation by steric crowding has previously been discussed^{11,12}. Ring-closure of the diketo-acid(VII) was effected with dilute alkali and the combined acids were esterified to furnish methyl 2-(1-naphthyl)-5-oxocyclopent-1-enylacetate(III) and methyl β -5-(1-naphthyl)-2-furylpropionate(V) in equal amounts as determined by the two carbomethoxy peaks at τ 6.50 and 6.33 respectively. The esters were separated by column chromatography and characterised by spectral data. As already stated, the methylene protons in the acetate side-chain in (III) appeared as a singlet at τ 6.92 and remained so down to -90° indicating a low energy barrier to rotation.

At this point, our attention was drawn to

a preliminary communication by Vijayasarithi and Krishna Rao⁸ in which they reported the isolation of a by-product, m.p. 95° in trace amount during acid-induced ethanolysis of furfurylidene *p*-methoxyacetophenone along with β -5-*p*-methoxyphenyl-2-furyl-propionic acid (and ester) as major product. They formulated it as 6-hydroxy-9-methoxy-2,3-dihydrophenalen-1-one (as hydrate IX) supposed to originate from a double cyclisation of the intermediate diketo-acid(VIII). The structure was based on elemental analysis and n.m.r. of both the ketone-hydrate(IX) and the derived dinitrophenylhydrazone. A more logical proposition is an acid-catalysed aldol condensation and dehydration to 2-*p*-methoxyphenyl-5-oxocyclopent-1-enylacetic acid(X) which is a typical reaction of 1,5-diketone leading to cyclohexenones^{1,8,14}. A sample of 4,7-diketo-7-*p*-methoxyphenylheptanoic acid(VIII) was, therefore, prepared by acidic hydrolysis of furfurylidene *p*-methoxyacetophenone^{1,5} and cyclised to the desired keto-acid(X) with aqueous alkali this time without encountering any furan-derivative. The acid was obtained as a monohydrate. m.p. 95° (from aqueous methanol)¹⁶ as well as an anhydrous form, m.p.

137° (from ethyl acetate-petroleum). The latter exhibited an n.m.r. spectrum, τ (CDCl₃, 90 MHz) 1.33 (1 H, br.s, CO₂H, exchangeable with D₂O), 2.50 (2 H, d, *J* 9Hz, 2ArH), 3.00 (2 H, d, *J* 9Hz, 2ArH), 6.15 (3H, s, OMe), 6.53 (2 H, s, CH₂CO₂H), 7.03 (2 H, m, CH₂), and 7.40 (2 H, m, CH₂) which was remarkably similar to that reported for the above-mentioned by-product⁸. The aromatic AB-quartet is very characteristic of a *p*-methoxyphenyl moiety as in (X) but rather a misfit for (IX). The m.p., however, tallied with that (95°) of our hydrated acid (as X). We were informed* that the m.p. of the by-product was taken before drying and the n.m.r. and elemental analysis were done probably with the dried sample. The dinitrophenylhydrazone of the keto-acid had m.p. 245° slightly lower than the reported one (252°) but its n.m.r. spectrum taken in trifluoroacetic acid was identical. peak by peak, to the one described for the by-product (see Experimental) with one exception that an extra methylene peak due the acetic acid side-chain in (X) was found partially buried in the methoxy peak at τ 5.90 and might have been missed by the previous workers. In all probability, therefore,

* Personal communication from Professor Krishna Rao who regretted his inability to provide us with any sample or spectrum for comparison.

the reported by-product in the ethanolysis reaction is 2-*p*-methoxyphenyl-5-oxocyclopent-1-enylacetic acid(X) although we could not be absolutely sure in absence of a direct comparison.

Experimental

All b.p.s and m.p.s are uncorrected. N.m.r. spectra were taken on 90 and 100 MHz machines for solutions in CDCl_3 (unless otherwise stated) with tetramethylsilane as internal standard. The low temperature n.m.r. spectra of (III) were taken on a Varian XL-100 100 MHz spectrometer in CD_2Cl_2 solution. Petroleum refers to a fraction of b.p. 40-60°. All organic extracts were dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate.

1-Acetylnaphthalene: Commercial 1-acetylnaphthalene containing 10% of 2-isomer was purified through conversion into picrate, recrystallisation, and subsequent regeneration of the ketone by passing the solution of picrate in benzene over a column of neutral alumina. 1-Acetylnaphthalene thus obtained was found to be pure by g.l.c.

Furfurylidene 1-Acetylnaphthalene (VI): Ethanolic sodium hydroxide (0.8%, 2 ml) was added to a solution of 1-acetylnaphthalene (20.0 g) and freshly distilled furfuraldehyde (10.0 g) in ethanol (70 ml). After 20 hr. at room temperature, a heavy gum settled down, the mother liquor was decanted off, the residual gum taken up in methanol (30 ml), cooled to 0°, and the supernatant mother liquor again decanted off. The process was repeated a second time, the orange gum taken up in ether, the ethereal solution washed successively with dilute hydrochloric acid and water, dried, and solvent evaporated to furnish the *furfurylidene derivative (VI)* as a red viscous oil (11.2 g); ν_{max} (CHCl_3) 1665, 1625, 1602, and 1554 cm^{-1} . All attempts to crystallise failed and this crude product was used in the next operation.

Hydrolysis of the Furfurylidene Derivative (VI): A mixture of the foregoing furfurylidene derivative (11.0 g), concentrated hydrochloric acid (12.0 ml), and ethanol (40.0 ml) was refluxed for 14 hr. Ethanol was removed at the water pump and the residue was boiled with a mixture of concentrated hydrochloric acid (12.0 ml), water (55.0 ml), and acetic acid (55.0 ml) for 2-3 hrs. The hot solution was filtered through glass wool and the filtrate was cooled to afford a dark heavy oil. The mother liquor was decanted on to the original black gum and the process was repeated several times⁷. At the end, the combined organic material (6.7 g) was dissolved in aqueous sodium hydrogen carbonate, neutral material removed by extraction with ether, and the solution acidified to give a mixture of the acids(IV) and (VII) which was taken up in methylene dichloride. Evaporation of the solvent furnished a gum (5.5 g) which proved to be a 50 : 50 mixture of the above two acids; ν_{max} (CHCl_3) 1715, 1688; ν_{max} ($\text{CHCl}_3 + \text{Et}_3\text{N}$) 1710, 1685, and 1600 cm^{-1} ; τ (100

MHz)-0.60 (1 H, s, CO_2H), 1.60 (1 H, m, ArH), 2.10-2.60 (6 H, m, 6ArH), 3.45 (d, J 3.3 Hz, 4'-H), 3.82 (d, J 3.3 Hz, 3'-H) (the last two peaks integrated for 1 H), and 6.6-7.50 (6 H, m, 3CH_2).

The above mixture (5.2 g) was taken up in aqueous 2% potassium hydroxide solution (500 ml) and heated in the water-bath for 1½ hr. The product was worked up in the usual way to afford a gum (4.7 g) which proved to be a 50 : 50 mixture of the acid(II) and (IV) by n.m.r.; τ (100 MHz)-0.47 (s, CO_2H), 1.65 (m, ArH), 2.00-2.82 (m, ArH), 3.42 (d, J 3.3 Hz), 3.82 (d, J 3.3 Hz), 6.89 (s, CH_2 - CO_2H), 6.98 (m, CH_2), 7-15-7.38 (m, CH_2) (because of the mixed nature, the proton count was not integral). The mixture of the acids (4.6 g) was esterified by refluxing methanolic 5% hydrogen chloride (80.0 ml) for 10 hr. and the esters distilled to yield an oil (4.4 g), b.p. 180-210°/0.3 mm; n.m.r. showed it to be a 50 : 50 mixture of the esters(III) and (V) and t.l.c. (silica gel, 60 : 40 petroleum-ethyl acetate) showed two distinct spots with R_f values 0.4 and 0.6 respectively. They were cleanly separated by chromatography on a silica gel column. The ester(V) (2.0 g) was eluted with 20 : 80 ether-petroleum while the ester(III) (2.0 g) with 95 : 5 ether-petroleum.

Methyl 2-(1-Naphthyl)-5-oxocyclopent-1-enylacetate (III): Methyl 2-(1-naphthyl)-5-oxocyclopent-1-enylacetate(III) was obtained in the previous experiment as a colourless viscous oil, b.p. 200-205°/0.3 mm (Found: C, 76.9; H, 5.9; M⁺, 280. Calc. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$; C, 77.2; H, 5.7%; M⁺, 280); ν_{max} (CHCl_3) 1740, 1708, 1650, and 1598 cm^{-1} ; λ_{max} (EtOH) 293 nm (log ϵ 4.1) (λ_{max} for I, 282 nm, log ϵ 4.0); τ (90 MHz) 2.10 (2 H, 2d, J 2 and 9 Hz, 2ArH), 2.20-2.75 (5 H, m, 5ArH), 6.50 (3 H, s, CO_2Me), 6.92 (2 H, s, $\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{Me}$), 6.96 (2 H, t, J 7 Hz, 3- CH_2), and 7.30 (2 H, t, J 7 Hz, 4- CH_2). The *dinitrophenylhydrazone* readily formed from benzene-methanol in red needles, m.p. 196° (Found: C, 62.35; H, 4.7; N, 12.2. Calc. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{20}\text{N}_4\text{O}_6$; C, 62.6; H, 4.35; N, 12.2%); τ (90 MHz)-1.02 (1 H, s, NH), 0.88 (1 H, d, J 1.5 Hz, ArH between two NO_2), 1.70 (1 H, 2d, J 1.5 and 9 Hz, ArH ortho to NO_2), 2.00-2.30 (4 H, m, 4 ArH), 2.35-2.70 (4 H, m 4 ArH), 6.41 (3 H, s, CO_2Me), 6.75 (2 H, s, $\text{CH}_2\text{CO}_2\text{Me}$), 6.85 (2 H, t, J 7 Hz, 3- H_2), and 7.00 (2 H, t, J 7 Hz, 4- H_2).

Methyl β -5-(1-Naphthyl)-2-furylpropionate (V): Methyl β -5-(1-naphthyl)-2-furylpropionate(V) was obtained as a colourless oil, b.p. 180°/0.3 mm (Found: C, 76.8; H, 5.8; M⁺, 280. Calc. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$; C, 77.2; H, 5.7%; M⁺, 280); ν_{max} (CHCl_3) 1735 and 1595 cm^{-1} ; τ (90 MHz) 1.61 (1 H, 2d, J 2 and 9 Hz, 8-H), 2.10-2.40 (3 H, m, 3ArH), 2.45-2.65 (3 H, m, 3ArH), 3.42 (1 H, d, J 3.3 Hz, 4-H), 3.82 (1 H, d, J 3.3 Hz, 3-H), 6.33 (3 H, s, CO_2Me), 6.90 (2 H, t, J 7 Hz, CH_2), and 7.28 (2 H, t, J 7 Hz, CH_2).

2-(*p*-Methoxyphenyl)-5-oxocyclopent-1-enylacetic Acid (X): 4.7-Diketo-7-*p*-methoxyphenylheptanoic acid(VIII) prepared by acidic hydrolysis of the furfurylidene derivative of *p*-methoxyacetophenone was cyclised with aqueous 2% potassium hydroxide at 100° for 1 hr. The alkaline solution on acidification furnished a crystalline product (0.90 g) which was crystallised from aqueous methanol in colourless plates, m.p. 95° (Found : C, 63.8; H, 6.25. Calc. for C₁₄H₁₄O₄, H₂O; C, 63.6; H, 6.1%); ν_{\max} (Nujol) 3450, 1700, and 1675 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (EtOH) 226 and 300 nm, log ϵ 3.98 and 4.31 respectively; τ (60M Hz) 2.35 (2 H, d, *J* 9 Hz, 2ArH), 2.85 (2 H, d, *J* 9 Hz, 2ArH), 5.10 (3 H, br. s, 3 × OH, exchangeable with D₂O), 6.15 (3 H, s, OMe), 6.52 (2 H, s, CH₂CO₂H), 7.00 (2 H, m, CH₂), and 7.30 (2 H, m, CH₂). It afforded a red dinitrophenylhydrazone, m.p. 245° (Found : C, 56.5; H, 4.5; N, 13.0. Calc. for C₂₀H₁₈O₇N₄; C, 56.3; H, 4.2; and N, 13.1%); τ (CF₃CO₂H)-0.5 (1 H, s, CO₂H), 0.70 (1 H, d, *J* 1.5 Hz, ArH), 1.37 (1 H, 2d, *J* 2 and 9 Hz, ArH), 2.20 (2 H, 2d, *J* 2 and 8 Hz, 2ArH), 2.40 (1 H, d, *J* 9 Hz, ArH), 2.70 (2 H, d, *J* 8 Hz, 2ArH), 5.85 (2 H, s, CH₂CO₂H), 5.90 (3 H, s, OMe), and 6.40 (4 H, br. s, 2CH₂).

The above hydrated acid(X) was recrystallised from ethyl acetate-petroleum in colourless plates, m.p. 137° (Found : C, 67.3; H, 5.7. Calc. for C₁₄H₁₄O₄; C, 68.2; H, 5.7%); ν_{\max} (Nujol) 1700 (sh) and 1680 cm⁻¹, (reported for IX; 1680 cm⁻¹); ν_{\max} (CHCl₃+Et₃N) 1680 cm⁻¹ and 1600 cm⁻¹; λ_{\max} (EtOH) 226 and 300 nm, log ϵ 4.06 and 4.43 respectively. The n.m.r. has already been discussed. The dinitrophenylhydrazone (red) had m.p. 245°.

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